

STUDIES IN SOME AROMATIC SULPHIDES AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

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Several aromatic sulphides have been treated with various reagents to determine the strength of the sulphur linkage in aromatic sulphides.

The reactions between benzene and naphthalene derivatives and chlorides of sulphur viz., sulphur mono- and dichloride and thionyl chloride have been studied by various workers and in most cases aromatic sulphides have been obtained (Onufrowicz, *Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 3355; Hirve *et al.*, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1933, **2**, 128; 1934, **3**, 551; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 101; Airan and Shah, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1940, **9**, 115). In order to determine the strength of the sulphur linkage on the one hand, and to ascertain the position of the same on the other, these sulphides have been treated with different reagents such as concentrated ammonia, cuprous chloride, silver nitrate, potassium dichromate and sulphuric acid, nitric acid (either dilute or concentrated or fuming) and bromine (the same references as above).

However, no particular author has made any attempt to study the strength of the sulphur linkage in the aromatic sulphides in a systematic manner. In this paper an attempt in such a direction has been made. Nitric acid (dilute and concentrated), bromine (in calculated quantities and in excess), chlorine, sulphuryl chloride and diazobenzene chloride have been allowed to react with the following aromatic sulphides and their acetyl derivatives. In those cases where the action of the above reagents on the following compounds has already been studied previously, it has not been repeated here.

- (1) 3:3'-Dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide (Hirve *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 101).
- (2) 4:4'-Dihydroxydinaphthyl trisulphide (Onufrowicz, *loc. cit.*).
- (3) 3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide (Airan and Shah, *loc. cit.*).
- (4) 3:3'-Dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide (Airan and Shah, *loc. cit.*).
- (5) 2:2'-Dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide (Onufrowicz, *loc. cit.*).
- (6) 2:2'-Dihydroxy-3:3'-dicarboxydinaphthyl sulphide (Airan and Shah, *loc. cit.*).
- (7-12) Acetyl derivatives of the above.

EXPERIMENTAL

(A.V. Rege carried out the experimental part of this work.)

The reaction between sulphuryl chloride and the sulphide was carried out in dry benzene by refluxing the mixture for about 1 hour at 50°-60°.

Chlorination, bromination and nitration (dilute nitric acid) were carried out in acetic acid solution of the sulphides and their acetyl derivatives.

Diazobenzene chloride was prepared according to the method described by Shah and co-workers (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1943, **11**, 85). The reactions were carried out in sodium hydroxide solutions of the sulphides and sodium bicarbonate solutions of their acetyl derivatives.

The results are shown in the following table.

TABLE I

The sulphide.	Reagent.	Product.	M. p.	Remarks.
(1) 3:3'-Dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide (2g.)	Sulphuryl chloride (5 c.c.)	5-Chlorosalicylic acid	167°	Known (Smith, <i>Ber</i> 1878 11, 1225)
Do	Cl ₂	3:5-Dichlorosalicylic acid	214°	Known (Smith <i>loc.cit.</i>)
Do	Diazobenzene chloride	5-Benzeneazo-salicylic acid	214°	Known (Zibell, <i>Ber.</i> , 1891, 24, 1696)
(2) 4:4'-Dihydroxydinaphthyl trisulphide (2g.)	Sulphuryl chloride (5 c.c.)	4-Chloronaphthol	116°	Known (Shah, <i>J. Univ. Bom.</i> , 1942, 10, 134)
Do	Cl ₂	2:4-Dichloro- <i>a</i> -naphthol	101°	Known (Cleve, <i>Ber.</i> , 1888, 21, 891)
Do	Br ₂ (2 c.c.)	2:4-Dibromo- <i>a</i> -naphthol	108°	Known (Biedermann, <i>Ber.</i> , 1873, 6, 1119)
Do	HNO ₃ (dil & conc.)	A plastic mass	—	—
Do	Diazobenzene chloride	4-Benzeneazo- <i>a</i> -naphthol	205°	Known (Typke, <i>Ber.</i> , 1877, 10, 1580)
(3) 3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide	Cl ₂	4-Chloro-2-acetyl- <i>a</i> -naphthol	117°	Known (Shah, <i>J. Univ. Bom.</i> , 1942, 10, 132)
Do	Cl ₂ (excess)	Trichloromethyl-(4-chloro-1-hydroxy)- <i>β</i> -naphthyl ketone	141°	New
Do	Br ₂ (1 c.c.)	4-Bromo-2-acetyl- <i>a</i> -naphthol	126°	Known (Hantzsch, <i>Ber.</i> , 1906, 39, 3097)
Do (2g.)	Br ₂ (4 c.c.)	Dibromomethyl (4-bromo-1-hydroxy)- <i>β</i> -naphthyl ketone.	201°	New
Do (2g.)	HNO ₃ (conc., 3 c.c.)	4-Nitro-2-acetyl- <i>a</i> -naphthol	154°	Known (Shah, <i>J. Univ. Bom.</i> , 1940, 9, 115)
(4) 3:3'-Dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide	Cl ₂	4-Chloro-1-oxy-2-naphthoic acid	229°	Known (Weil, <i>Ber.</i> , 1911, 44, 3061)
Do	Cl ₂ (excess)	2:2:3:3:4:4-Pentachloro-1-oxy-naphthalene tetrahydride	152°	Known (Zincke, <i>Ber.</i> , 1888, 21, 1044)
Do (2g)	Br ₂ 15 c.c.)	4-Bromo-1-oxy-2-naphthoic acid	241°	Known (Weil, <i>Ber.</i> , 1911, 44, 2700)
Do (2g.)	HNO ₃ (conc., 4 c.c.)	2:4-Dinitro- <i>a</i> -naphthol	137°	Known (Shah, <i>J. Univ. Bom.</i> , 1940, 9, 115)
(5) 2:2'-Dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide (2 g.)	Sulphuryl chloride (5 c.c.)	1-Chloro- <i>β</i> -naphthol	70°	Known (Armstrong, <i>Chem. News</i> , 1889, 69, 225)
Do	Cl ₂	Do	70°	Do
(6) 2:2'-Dihydroxy-3:3'-dicarboxydinaphthyl sulphide	Cl ₂	1-Chloro-2-oxy-3-naphthoic acid	230°	Known (Gradenwitz, <i>Ber.</i> , 1894, 27, 2622)
Do	Cl ₂ (excess)	1:1:3:3:4:4-Pentachloro-2-oxynaphthalene tetrahydride	114°	Known (Zincke, <i>Ber.</i> , 1888, 21, 3379)
Do (5 g.)	Br ₂ (excess, 12c.c.)	1:6-Dibromo-2-oxy-3-naphthoic acid	251°	New
Do (2 g)	HNO ₃ (conc., 5 c.c.)	1-Nitro-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid	230°	Known (Shah, <i>J. Univ. Bom.</i> , 1940, 9, 115)

TABLE I (contd.)

The sulphide.	Reagent.	Product.	M. p.	Remarks.
(7) 3:3'-Dicarboxy-4:4'-diacetoxydiphenyl sulphide (2 g.)	Sulphuryl chloride (5 c.c.)	Original compound	—	No reaction.
Do	Cl ₂	Do		Do
Do (5 g.)	Br ₂ (6 c.c.)	3:3'-Dibromo-4:4'-diacetoxy-5:5'-dicarboxydiphenyl sulphide	276°	Known (Hirve, <i>J. Amer. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1935, 57 , 101)
Do (2 g.)	HNO ₃ (dil., 4 c.c.)	5-Nitrosalicylic acid	221°	Known, Do
Do (5 g.)	HNO ₃ (conc., 10 c.c.)	2:4:6-Trinitrophenol	120°	Known, Do
Do	Diazobenzene chloride	2:4:6-Tribenzeneazophenol	215°	Known (Grandmougin, <i>Ber.</i> , 1907, 40 , 3450)
(8) 4:4'-Diacetoxydinaphthyl sulphide (2 g.)	Sulphuryl chloride (5 c.c.)	Original compound		No reaction
Do	Cl ₂	Do		Do
Do (2 g.)	Br ₂ (8 c.c.)	A plastic mass		
Do (5 g.)	HNO ₃ (20 c.c.)	Do		
(9) 3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-diacetoxydinaphthyl sulphide (2 g.)	Sulphuryl chloride (5 c.c.)	Original compound		Do
Do	Cl ₂	Do		Do
Do (2 g.)	Br ₂ (5 c.c.)	Dibromomethyl-(4-bromo-1-hydroxy- β -naphthyl ketone	201°	New
Do (2 g.)	HNO ₃ (dil. 5 c.c.)	4-Nitro-2-acetyl- α -naphthol	154°	Known (Shah, <i>J. Univ. Bom.</i> , 1940 9 , 115)
(9) 3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-diacetoxydinaphthyl sulphide	HNO ₃ (conc., 4 c.c.)	4-Nitro-2-acetyl- α -naphthol	154°	Known (Shah, <i>J. Univ. Bom.</i> , 1940, 9 , 115)
(10) 3:3'-Dicarboxy-4:4'-diacetoxydinaphthyl sulphide (2 g.)	Sulphuryl chloride (3 c.c.)	Original compound		No action
Do	Cl ₂	Do		Do
Do (2 g.)	Br ₂ (5 c.c.)	4-Bromo-1-oxy-2-naphthoic acid	241°	Known (Weil, <i>Ber.</i> , 1911, 44 , 2700)
Do (2 g.)	HNO ₃ (dil., 6 c.c.)	2:4-Dinitro- α -naphthol	136°	Known (Shah, <i>J. Univ. Bom.</i> , 1940, 9 , 115)
Do (2 g.)	HNO ₃ (conc., 5 c.c.)	Do	Do	Do
Do	Diazobenzene chloride	4-Benzeneazo-1-oxy-2-naphthoic acid	192°	Known (Neitzki, <i>Ber.</i> 1887, 20 , 1275)
(11) 2:2'-Diacetoxydinaphthyl sulphide (2 g.)	Sulphuryl chloride (5 c.c.)	Original compound		No reaction.
Do	Cl ₂	2:2'-Diacetoxy-6:6'-dichlorodinaphthyl sulphide	198°	New
		2:2'-Dihydroxy-6:6'-dichlorodinaphthyl sulphide (after hydrolysis of the above compound)	224°	New
Do (5 g.)	Br ₂ (10 c.c.)	2:2'-Dihydroxy-6:6'-dibromodinaphthyl sulphide	201°	New
		2:2'-Dihydroxy-6:6'-dibromodinaphthyl sulphide (after hydrolysis of the above compound)	224°	New

TABLE I (contd.)

The sulphide.	Reagent.	Product.	M.p.	Remarks.
2:2'-Dihydroxy-6:6'-dibromodinaphthyl sulphide (2 g.)	Br ₂ (0.8 c.c.)	1:6-Dibromo-β-naphthol	124°	Known
Do (2 g.)	HNO ₃ (dil., 7 c.c.)	2:2'-Diacetoxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide	210°	New
Do (4 g.)	HNO ₃ (conc., 10 c.c.)	Do	Do	Do
(12) 2:2'-Diacetoxy-3:3'-dicarboxydinaphthyl sulphide (2 g.)	Sulphuryl chloride (5 c.c.)	Original compound		No reaction
Do	Cl ₂	Do		Do
Do (5 g.)	Br ₂ (12 c.c.)	1:6-Dibromo-2-oxy-3-naphthoic acid	251°	New
Do (2 g.)	HNO ₃ (dil., 5 c.c.)	2:2'-Diacetoxy-3:3'-dicarboxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide	Did not melt up to 300°	New
2:2'-Diacetoxy-3:3'-dicarboxydinaphthyl sulphide (2 g.)	HNO ₃ (conc., 5 c.c.)	2:2'-Diacetoxy-3:3'-dicarboxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide	Did not melt up to 330°	New
Do	Diazobenzene chloride	2:2'-Dihydroxy-3:3'-dicarboxy-6:6'-dibenzeneazo-dinaphthyl sulphide.	300°	New

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